

Considerations about the Implementation of Mini-MAP Architectures on a Front-End Processor

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Abstract

The interconnection of computers in networks, such as the Manufacturing Automation Protocols (MAP), brought the need to guarantee an optimum use of the resources involved. The optimization can be achieved by designing the network interface as a front-end processor (FEP) and by implementing a customized nucleus for supporting multi-layer protocol applications. In this paper is described the implementation of a FEP with a nucleus oriented for protocol applications. The description covers the most important design issues for both hardware and software. It is discussed the options adopted considering the characteristics of protocol applications such as layering, hierarchical modeling, inter-process communication and time constraints, among others. The immediate application in sought for the developed FEP is the industrial automation in a mini-MAP network.

Keywords: Manufacturing Automation Protocols, MAP, Mini-MAP, Front-End Processor, Real-Time Nucleus, Nucleus Primitives.

1 Introduction

The generalized use of computers in industrial automation and the consequent need for connectivity between them, resulted in the use of computer networks as building blocks supporting communications for manufacturing in Computer Integrated Manufacturing (CIM) [1] and related technologies like Computer Aided Design (CAD) [2], Computer Aided Manufacturing (CAM) [3] and Computer Aided Production Planning (CAPP) [4], among others [5] [6].

The Manufacturing Automation Protocols (MAP) architecture [7], based on the ISO (International Standards Organization) Reference Model for Open Systems Interconnection [8], is a set of standard protocols proposed for the industrial environment. MAP architecture includes alternatives such as full-MAP and mini-MAP [9]. The full-MAP is a backbone solution suitable for connecting medium size computers and mainframes at the top management level. The mini-MAP alternative is more appropriate for plant and cell levels in which real-time constraints exist [10].

Front-end processors (FEPs) are an adequate hardware solution for implementing

computer network interfaces, such as the mini-MAP, that presents particular design characteristics [11].

As far as the software is concerned, a protocol application, such as the mini-MAP protocol layers, needs a nucleus with some operating system facilities to run on a front-end processor [12].

In this paper, we present the most important design issues concerning a FEP suitable for protocol applications with the target application in sought being the industrial automation [13].

In the following sections are presented the FEP architecture, its hardware and the nucleus basic design issues considering the multi-layer protocol structure running on it.

2 Front-End Processor Architecture

The architecture of a front-end processor (FEP) for supporting multi-layer protocol execution is basically composed of:

- A specialized hardware (Figure 1); and

- a multi-layer architecture executing under control of a specialized nucleus (Figure 2)

The FEP's hardware includes a dedicated circuit for network control and management and a local microprocessor with computational power to guarantee efficient execution of the multi-task structure.

The FEP multi-layer architecture is composed by a nucleus, the host communication mechanism and the protocol layers executing the corresponding protocol machines. The nucleus provides operating system facilities (multi-tasking, inter-task communication, priorities, other) to support the concurrent execution of the protocol layers. The host communication mechanics is responsible for the communication between host at the level chosen by the software design.

Although the FEP's hardware and the FEP's software support (i.e.: nucleus) can be either bought or designed independently, our aim was to arrive to a solution which considers the specific application in sought. In effect, we expect to optimize the software support and to adapt the hardware to the needs derived from running network communication protocols.

In the following discussion, we present in more detail the relevant aspects and the design options for both FEP's hardware and multi-layer architecture.

3 The FEP's Hardware

The main building blocks of the FEP's hardware are the following (Figure 1) [14]:

- A local microprocessor (80186 - 10MHz):
- An on-chip network controller; and
- A multi-access memory.

The integrated network controller used is the MC68824 [15] token-bus controller which implements the IEEE 802.4 standard [16] corresponding to the MAC (Medium Access Control) and part of the LLC (Logical Link Control) layers of the MAP architecture [17]. Since

the target is the mini-MAP implementation, on-board circuits provide access to the physical medium for baseband transmission at 5 Mbit/s/sec.

The network controller (NC) is controlled by the local central processing unit (CPU) through data structures for initialization, transmission and reception of frames in the common memory. NC's access to the common memory is done by direct memory access (DMA) and limited in the number of cycles in order to avoid excessive locking of the memory. In effect, the on-board memory can be accessed simultaneously by the host, the local CPU and the network controller and provision has to be taken to guarantee fair access to all these elements.

The size for the DRAMs used is 2x512K bytes which is estimated to be enough for the target implementation (Mini-MAP), but also for EPA MAP and even full-MAP ones. Application programs could eventually fit on the on-board memory depending on their size and, of course, on the designer's option.

The FEP has a page switching mechanism used by the host to access the on-board memory which is divided in up to 16 pages of 32K bytes. Once defined the page/window of access to the memory, the host can read/write through it concurrently with the local CPU and the NC. There is no hardwired access restriction to any of the elements accessing the memory and all logical mappings on it are defined by the application running on the system.

Another application related option for the hardware, was the elimination of on-board firmware. In effect, all programs are downloaded by the host through the window mechanism. This design alternative is applicable to the case of network protocols which normally are steady-running applications requiring few rebooting procedures.

4 Software Basic Issues

The next discussion presents the basic issues of the software installed in the FEP, focusing on the following points:

Figure 1: FEP's Hardware Architecture

- Memory organization;
- Nucleus options; and
- Host communication.

There is a variety of possible memory arrangements and nucleus options [18] [19] [20]. Therefore, the relevant question depicted is the FEP set of facilities which best suits the multi-layer protocol structure under the restrictions we have ourselves imposed.

4.1 Memory Organization

The FEP's memory space is organized as an array of tasks and working areas as follows (Figure 3):

- Nucleus;
- User tasks (protocol layers and/or application programs); and
- Working area and host window.

All tasks, including the nucleus itself, are downloaded by the host during the initialization process using this window mechanism.

This feature implies that the host controls all the initialization phase of the FEP with the

number of tasks downloaded depending on the application and memory space available. Once loaded, the execution control is passed to the nucleus and the tasks are scheduled according with the scheduling policy, priority and other parameters defined and controlled by the nucleus.

The memory space following the tasks is allocated by the nucleus as follows:

- A heap; and
- A window for host/FEP communication.

The heap is used for dynamic memory allocation, in which the nucleus and the tasks can request variable-size blocks of memory. Some of this allocated memory is used by the MAC layer software to house the initialization and control structures for the NC.

The communications window is used by the nucleus to house a common data structure, through which, using software handshaking, data buffers are exchanged between the host and the FEP.

4.2 Nucleus

Nuclei presents different implementation strategies according with their target application [21] [22] [23]. For instance, they can

Figure 2: FEP's Multi-Layer Architecture

be modeled hierarchically, as done in some operating systems, can be object-oriented and can be modeled according with the required functionality (programming-in-the-large) or according with the merit and efficiency of the implementation (programming-in-the-small).

The main features which characterizes them are:

- Scheduling policy;
- Inter-process communication;
- Memory allocation; and
- Temporization.

4.2.1 Scheduling

The alternatives which exist for the scheduling policy are the following [24]:

- Preemptive with one queue, scheduled by a defined process key;
- Preemptive with multiple queues, scheduled with different priorities;
- First-come first-served (FCFS) (not preemptive);
- Time-sharing; and
- Other special purpose variations.

The protocol architecture being focused has a hierarchical architecture [11] in which a set of particular characteristics holds (Figure 4).

The first characteristic is that the tasks are independent and can be executed concurrently. We then have two possible cases:

- The layer is modeled as a single task; or

Figure 3: Task and Resource Allocation on Memory

- The layer is modeled as a multiple task structure.

For the single task model (by layer), the assumption is straightforward due to the particular characteristics of the ISO proprietary models used in most protocol implementations.

In the multiple-task model, the tasks are either instances of the protocol machine or the manager of the inter-layer communication. Anyhow, these tasks are driven by events which trigger sequences of actions.

The second characteristic of the protocol applications is the time constraints involved. Here, we have a performance parameter. In effect, the time constraints are recoverable by the protocol itself and the main effect of the scheduling policy chosen is the medium performance achieved.

In summary, for protocols we have non-periodic tasks with recoverable time constraints. The scheduling policy we have chosen was then preemptive, in order to guarantee fair execution of multiple independent

tasks, with priority. The priority stands as a designer option to keep on with time constraints whenever it becomes necessary.

The primitives implemented which support the task scheduling are:

- `x_get_priority;`
- `x_set_priority;`
- `x_sleep;`
- `x_lock;`
- `x_unlock;` and;
- `_swap.`

The `x_sleep` primitive allows a task to suspend itself for a defined period.

The `x_lock` and `x_unlock` primitives allow the tasks to suspend preemptive context changing, and can be used, for example, to guarantee exclusive access to shared data structures.

Figure 4: Typical Protocol Application

The `x_swap` primitive forces a context change. This allows the tasks to effect cooperative context changing as an alternative to the preemptive context changing normally used.

4.2.2 Inter-process Communication (IPC)

The operating systems mechanisms most commonly used for message exchange and synchronization between process are queues, shared memory and semaphores [24] [25] [26].

For protocol applications, we have an hierarchical structure with layers passing messages through service primitives [25]. In this case, for both single and multiple task models, the basic mechanism required for process communication or, in our case, task communication, is a message-passing one. Semaphores are not essential for protocol applications where tasks are a sequence of independent actions and seldom dispute a common resource.

From the user point of view, there are two possible alternatives for using the message passing mechanism:

- A structured message is exchange; or

- a buffer (pointer) is passed with a message stored on it.

The option between these alternatives is very important for the performance of the FEP, in that:

- The first involves the transfer of blocks of memory; and
- In protocol applications, we have multiple layers with possible multiple tasks per layer.

Considering such characteristics, our design option for the IPC was a non-blocking message-passing (send/receive) mechanism in which the tasks prepare messages and pass pointers to these to the nucleus which installs these pointers in queues.

The nucleus offers two primitives for IPC:

- `x_send_message`; and
- `x_get_message`.

The send/receive mechanism is equivalent to multiple queues with a FIFO discipline individually associated with the tasks.

4.2.3 Memory Allocation

There are different memory allocation/releasing methods based on segmentation, free fixed size blocks and lists of free variable sized areas [27].

In our protocol application we have chosen to implement the method based on a list of free variable-sized areas. Each free area has a header with its size and management control information.

The tasks can request any quantity of memory up to 64 Kbytes. Internally, the nucleus allocates memory in blocks of 16 bytes to allow faster list processing (all address and size calculations can be made using the segment part of the 80186 address).

The primitives available for memory allocation are:

- `x_get_memory`; and
- `x_return_memory`.

Due to the hardware limitations, there is no memory protection involved with memory allocation. This implies that, during the debug phase of the development, program errors can crash the interface. As a given FEP will normally execute a non-variable set of software, the use of memory protection would introduce an overhead without giving any benefits.

4.2.4 Temporization

Temporization is an essential facility for protocol applications. This results from the fact that temporization is used to a great degree and its characteristics influence the general performance.

The most important characteristics which are recommendable for the temporization are the following:

- To have a good time resolution, in order to allow fine adjustments in the lower-level layers of the protocol application where the time constraints are harder; and
- To have a soft implementation in order to minimize the execution time used to

maintain and update the multiple active timers.

Implicit timers are an alternative approach for protocols. For instance, timers associated with frames are efficient for low-level protocol layers, but they lose their effectiveness for high-level protocol layers.

Another alternative is to have a special task for temporization [25]. The special task communicates with the others through special ports which don't exchange message but, instead, block the tasks in order to generate the expected timeout.

In our implementation, timeouts are independent events which can be used to synchronize tasks. Basically, the temporization is implemented by defining an array of structures for controlling time and the resources (tasks) associated with them. For each clock interruption these structures are updated using an efficient algorithm of the type *uptade all by updating the first entry*.

The temporization facility is provided to the tasks by various primitives:

- `x_set_timer`;
- `x_get_timer`;
- `x_reset_timer`;
- `x_read_timer`; and
- `x_kill_timer`;

These primitives have the following characteristics:

- Multiple timers can be set by a task;
- Each timer is identified by a tag; and
- Timeouts are either signaled to sleeping tasks or can be explicitly recovered by an active task.

4.2.5 Task Synchronization

Task synchronization is provided by latching events occurring in the system [28]. By use of

the primitive `x_wait_event`, a task can suspend itself until an event occurs.

The possible events considered for implementation which are used in protocol applications are:

- Message arrival; and
- Timeout.

Another task synchronization facility available is the one to put a task to sleep for a fixed period of time (primitive `x_sleep`).

4.3 Host Communication

In the hierarchical structure which exists in protocol applications, it is only the highest layer running on the FEP which will exchange messages with the host. However, in practice, any task should be able to send status and error messages directly to the host.

To enable this, the primitives `x_send_message` and `x_get_message` used for inter-task communication are also used for exchanging messages between an FEP's task and the host. For communications purposes, the host is identified as a group of processes whose task identities are negative numbers. The host process -1 identifies a host console process to which any FEP task can send error and status messages.

On the host side, a driver is needed to get the message in the FEP's working memory and to pass it to the specific process at the host environment. This driver binds all hardware and operating system dependencies of the implementation and, also, knows the data structures which house the messages on the FEP.

By convention, the common data structure used for message passing is located in the last window of the FEP memory. This data structure is divided into two equal sections, one for incoming messages and one for outgoing messages.

5 Conclusion

The design of a FEP for protocol applications was optimized according with the specific char-

acteristics of the multi-layer architecture and protocol machine executing behavior.

We have shown that the main supporting facilities for a nucleus can be customized to the protocol case after an accurate analysis of its needs and that many services and attributes can be fairly dropped leading to a more compact and efficient nucleus.

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